

Dear Climate Farm Demo Community,

Exciting times are upon us as we launched the first annual campaign of on-farm demonstration events across our extensive network of 1,500 farms spread across Europe in 27 project partner countries. The upcoming demonstrations will cover a range of topics, including climate mitigation and adaptation measures, GHG audit results, and the climate action plans of the demonstration farmers.

Participants will have abundant opportunities for discussions, engaging with host farmers and exchanging ideas with the guidance of advisors. In the ClimateFarmDemo project, our demonstration farmers play a key role in integrating climate smart farming practices and sharing the outcomes with peers, fostering essential peer-to-peer knowledge exchange to advance sustainable agriculture.

Participate & Learn more

Excitingly, a handful of demonstrations may unfold in the coming months, offering a sneak peek into our initiatives. However, the majority of these engaging demonstrations are meticulously scheduled to commence from the spring of 2024 onwards. Stay tuned for a wave of inspiring and informative events that will shape the future of sustainable farming practices!

Regular updates on planned events for each country will be available over the next eleven months.

For those keen to participate or learn more, **[click here](#)**.

The winter of 2023-2024 will mark the start of the very first 'wave' of demonstration events for the project! Expecting between 700 and 800 demonstrations by the end of summer 2024 and a total of 4,500 events overall, the aim is to demonstrate the economic viability of climate smart farming practices and encourage widespread adoption to combat climate change.

Christine Berger
IDELE and Operational Co-ordinator ClimateFarmDemo

Demonstrating climate solutions on commercial farms across Europe will accelerate the adoption of these solutions by European farmers. Farm demonstrations are a recognised means of enabling farmers to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to adopt new practices and to modify their farming practices in the face of both challenges and opportunities.

Tom O'Dwyer
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Explore further by clicking here to delve into the details and expand your knowledge!

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